

On Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming the devil is in... the demand

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Acknowledgements

We gratefully acknowledge the helpful review for this brief by Mathieu Mal (European Environmental Bureau) and Tristano Bacchetti De Gregoris (SAE Innova). The arguments presented in this brief are solely those of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of the reviewers.

Funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement n° 101112951.

The implementation of carbon farming practices on European farms and in European forests is key to decarbonisation and farm resilience, for forest stands adaptation to climate change and for contributing to our strategic independence.

Certifying and financing practices that reduce emissions and store carbon is the objective of the [CRCF \(Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming\) regulation](#). It is therefore an opportune moment to [draw lessons from six years of experience](#) with a similar standard in France: the “Label Bas-Carbone” (Low Carbon Label - LBC). The results show that striking the right balance between scientific rigour and accessibility for stakeholders has led to the development of a substantial range of projects. However, the real challenge is to build sufficient and appropriate demand to finance the projects. There is no miracle solution, but complementary financing channels could emerge.

The search for a balance between scientific rigour and accessibility has enabled stakeholders to develop a substantial range of low-carbon projects.

In six years, nearly 2,000 forest owners and 4,000 French farmers have committed to carbon farming practices through the LBC, with an estimated potential impact of 8 Mt CO₂ combining emission reductions and carbon sequestration. These mainly involve: 1) forestry projects with afforestation and restoration of degraded forests, and 2) agricultural projects aimed in particular at optimising herd management in cattle farming, as well as fertilisation management and the introduction of intermediate cover crops in arable farming.

The LBC's operating model is the result of a collaborative process between field stakeholders, research and administration to find compromises

that aim to ensure the scientific integrity of the system while maintaining its practicality for stakeholders in the field. This co-construction, which has been in place since the LBC's inception, is one of the reasons for the commitment of stakeholders in the agricultural and forestry sectors, which is worth highlighting: two-thirds of the projects are directly supported by organisations from the sectors, such as agricultural and forestry cooperatives, technical institutes and forest managers. Their role is essential because the projects require technical support that is as close as possible to farmers and forest owners. The LBC has thus also played a major role in increasing the sectors' expertise on climate issues and in the adoption of low-carbon practices.

However, demand is currently insufficient to finance all carbon farming projects.

While the supply of projects has grown exponentially until 2024, the main concerns today relate to project financing. Demand currently covers only half of the LBC approved projects.

There are two types of demand:

- Voluntary demand from companies choosing, without any regulatory constraints, to finance projects as close as possible to their territory or sector of activity. This demand is usually linked to 'contribution claims'.
- Compliance demand, mainly from airlines, which are required to offset half of their domestic flight emissions in Europe. This demand finances at least 40% of annual LBC volumes and is therefore a key driver of the French market.

In general, French credits are pre-financed at a much higher price than international credits: 31€/t CO₂ on average for LBC, compared with 8 €/tCO₂ internationally. This price difference weighs on demand, even though LBC remains attractive to voluntary buyers thanks to the credibility and the local solution it brings.

Serious concerns about the financing of agricultural projects...

The difficulties in financing LBC projects are currently concentrated in the agricultural sector and pose major risks to the future of the scheme. Not only are farmers already engaged in carbon farming practices at risk of not receiving the promised financial support, but a sense of mistrust is also taking hold, slowing down the commitment of new farmers to any low-carbon scheme.

According to feedback from stakeholders in France, the funding shortfall for agricultural projects can be explained by various challenges:

- It is difficult for the LBC to mobilise the downstream part of the agricultural value chain. Due to a lack of clarity on the claims associated with LBC carbon credits, agri-food industries prefer to encourage farmers through contractual arrangements such as price premiums.
- Agricultural projects are generally less attractive than forestry projects:
 - Agricultural credits are more expensive: around 45€/tCO₂ compared to forestry projects, which cost 25-35€/tCO₂; this

is a particularly significant obstacle for compliance demand, which is primarily price-sensitive.

- The narrative associated with low-carbon agricultural projects is more complex and less attractive than that of tree planting in forestry projects. This has a direct impact on voluntary financing.

Drawing lessons from the LBC to stimulate CRCF demand.

At European level, the voluntary carbon market is the most likely short-term financing option, although the CRCF was initially developed to channel various types of financing: voluntary carbon market, internal financing within value chains, compliance requirements, public subsidies (e.g. from the CAP), etc.

However, voluntary demand is likely to remain limited: economic actors are taking a wait-and-see approach to their environmental commitments in a fluctuating economic, regulatory and societal context, which is likely to continue despite the potential trust and credibility provided by the European Commission's endorsement of the CRCF. In general, the CRCF is likely to face the same difficulties as LBC, particularly in terms of price: European projects will remain more expensive than international ones.

Voluntary demand will therefore need to be stimulated, but it will likely remain insufficient. The Commission is considering creating a [buyers' club](#) to facilitate private fundraising. This proposal to bring together economic actors willing to make a long-term voluntary commitment is a concrete

and interesting way of stimulating demand, but it is unlikely to be sufficient to cover the entire supply. If the example of the LBC shows us that voluntary demand is not sufficient to finance all approved projects, this will be even more true in the European context, where carbon projects with very ambitious impact targets are already being submitted (particularly under the [Verra standard](#)).

The involvement of public authorities will be essential to ensure that the demand meets the needs.

Options could include:

- The mobilisation of public funds (European or from Member States) to complement private funds, for example within the framework of the buyer's club, would constitute significant added value. It would enable the leveraging of private funds or reduce investors risk, for example by establishing purchase commitments at a minimum price.
- The prospect of compliance demand must also be explored. The French example shows that imposing obligations on actors in other sectors can help to structure the carbon market. Although the project for an ETS-type market for the agri-food sector is no longer on the agenda, it could re-surface in the longer term. In the meantime, other options can be considered, as in the French case.
- Public authorities can also act to directly support project supply by covering part of the implementation costs, which would help to reduce tCO₂ prices. In France, subsidies are currently available for farm GHG diagnostics, the development of carbon farming action plans

and support for their implementation. CAP subsidies could also play this role.

- Finally, public procurement is another lever worth exploring, and the upcoming 2026 revision of the European rules governing it represents an opportunity to be seized.

The implementation of CRCF is a milestone for the climate transition in the sector. Still, major points of vigilance remain regarding the actual funding it will provide to farmers, notably if relying exclusively on the voluntary approach. The European Commission would be wise to prepare for a stronger public intervention already now.